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Students Evaluation of the Virtualspeech Platform: A Pilot Study

Background

This report is an evaluation of students' experience on Virtualspeech. This platform simulates a real-life scenario where students practice their public speaking skills in front of a VR audience. Throughout the course "The Art of Applying Psychology", students are divided into three teams with the goal of developing a business idea. At the end of the course, the CEOs of each team pitch the idea to a panel of investors. We offered students the opportunity to practice their pitch on Virtualspeech during a one-hour session. Based on their feedback, we assess whether Virtualspeech should be implemented in the course to aid students in improving their public speaking skills.

Procedure

Nine students from the course "The Art of Applying Psychology" participated in a one-hour individual session where they practiced their pitches on Virtualspeech. Participation was mandatory for CEOs ($N = 3$) and vice-CEOs ($N = 3$) of each team and it was voluntary for other team members ($N = 3$). Before the session, all students created a VirtualSpeech account and emailed their presentation slides to the experimenter, who uploaded them on VirtualSpeech. Upon arrival at the lab, students completed a qualtrics questionnaire divided in three parts. The first part named "Scoring Skills before" (SSB) included a subjective evaluation of nine general skills rated on a 5-point likert scale. The second part named "Before Pilot" (BP) consisted of seven questions regarding their aims and expectations on the upcoming VR session. The third part named "After Pilot" (AP) was characterized by six questions about their experience during the VirtualSpeech session. After completing SSB and BP, the experimenter measured students' interpupillary distance and manually adjusted the setting on the VR oculus. Subsequently, students wore the VR oculus and were instructed how to navigate the VirtualSpeech interface.

On VirtualSpeech, students were directed to the conference room “Lecture Hall 2-D”, and they were recommended to practice their elevator pitch in this environment at least two times. When the final speech analysis results were calculated, students were told to remove the VR oculus and complete the AP section of the qualtrics questionnaire. Finally, as a follow-up, the experimenter asked students to share any further impressions or remarks about their experience on VirtualSpeech.

Results

Qualtrics Questionnaire

SSB

This subsection contains a visual inspection of SSB data rated on a 5-point likert scale (1 = very poor - 5 = excellent) by the nine students.

Figure 1

Scores Distribution of SSB-1 "How would you rate your communication skills? "

Figure 2

Scores Distribution of SSB-2 “How would you rate your presentation skills?”.

Figure 3

Scores Distribution of SSB-3 “How would you rate your leadership skills?”.

Figure 4

Scores Distribution of SSB-4 “How would you rate your active listening skills?”.

Figure 5

Scores Distribution of SSB-5 “How would you rate your negotiation skills?”.

Figure 6

Scores Distribution of SSB-6 “How would you rate your networking skills?”.

Figure 7

Scores Distribution of SSB-7 “How would you rate your connection with colleagues?”

Figure 8

Scores Distribution of SSB-8 “How would you rate your understanding of soft skills?”.

Figure 9

Scores Distribution of SSB-9 “How would you rate your confidence with soft skills?”.

BP

This subsection contains a visual inspection of BP data rated by the nine students.

Figure 10

Scores Distribution of BP-1 “Have you completed a self paced training course before?”.

Figure 11

Scores Distribution of BP-2 “What is your primary reason for enrolling into this L&D program?”.

Note. Reasons specified for “Others” included that it is a mandatory requirement for the course.

Figure 12

Scores Distribution of BP-3 “Which soft skills would you like to improve ? (you can choose multiple options)”.

Figure 13

Scores Distribution of BP-4 “Are you ready to start this learning journey?”.

Figure 14

Scores Distribution of BP-5 “What would be the ideal outcome of this learning program once you have completed it?”.

Note. Reasons specified for “Other” included to increase confidence after this presentation.

AP

This subsection contains a visual inspection of AP data rated by the nine students.

Figure 15

Scores Distribution of AP-1 “What did you like about Virtualspeech?”

Note. Reasons specified for “Other” included that it feels less anxious than performing in front of a real audience.

Figure 16

Scores Distribution of AP-2 “Which practice exercise did you find most valuable?”

Note. Reasons specified for “Other” included the AI generated questions.

Figure 17

Score Distribution of AP-3 “Do you think your skills have improved on Virtualspeech?”

Figure 17

Score Distribution of AP-4 “Do you think your confidence to use your skills has increased with Virtualspeech?”

Figure 17

Score Distribution of AP-5 “Do you think Virtualspeech is a useful addition to your learning offering?”

Speech Analysis

This section contains a visual inspection of the various speech analysis parameters recorded from three participants who fully completed two practice rounds.

Figure 18

Eye Contact Scores Following Practice Round 1 and Practice Round 2 From Three Participants.

Figure 19

Words Per Minute Following Practice Round 1 and Practice Round 2 From Three Participants.

Figure 20

Percentage of Voice Volume Following Practice Round 1 and Practice Round 2 From Three Participants.

Figure 21

Percentage of Filler Words to All Words Following Practice Round 1 and Practice Round 2

From Three Participants.

Figure 22

Listenability Score Following Practice Round 1 and Practice Round 2 From Three Participants.

Figure 23

Percentage of Overall Score Following Practice Round 1 and Practice Round 2 From Three Participants.

Qualitative Data

This section includes a summary of the qualitative responses recorded from both the qualtrics questionnaire and the experimenter's follow-up after the Virstualspeech session. Most participants were positively impressed by the experience. In the follow-up question, eight out of nine participants said that they would use the platform as a tool for practicing presentations if they were offered the opportunity. One participant remained skeptical because a single session is not enough to evaluate the usefulness of the experience, and two other participants remarked that having more time or more sessions could perhaps be more beneficial.

Judgements about the immersiveness of the VR experience were mixed. Participants that never tried VR before reported higher feelings of immersiveness, and one of them even reported

feelings of distraction because they felt too immersed in the environment. However, others identified several distracting elements that limited the immersiveness of their experience. Regarding the VR lecture hall environment, there has been criticism regarding avatars' features. For example, two reported that avatars movements were glitchy and that their continuous smiles seemed fake. Furthermore, several noticed an avatar in the front row that would continuously sip from a mug. These participants elaborated that such features created a fictitious atmosphere which sometimes distracted their focus from the flow of the pitch. However, others perceived this unrealistic environment as an advantage because it made them feel less anxious than being in front of a human audience. Someone even mentioned that with enough practice, Viirtualspeech could help them to get rid of presentation anxiety. Immersiveness was sometimes limited also by spatial and self-referential features. One participant pointed out that the size of the VR stage would give them the urge to walk around, but they could not do so because the actual room was too small and their overall movements were limited. Moreover, during an actual presentation they are used to look at their own hand gestures when explaining the slides, however, this was not possible on Virtualspeech.

Reports about the type of interactive feedback provided by Virtualspeech was also ambivalent. Some participants disliked the immediate feedback provided when voice volume and eye-contact are low. They mentioned that it was unexpected, so it interrupted their flow. On the other hand, others thought that receiving immediate feedback was advantageous, and they mentioned that they could imagine this benefiting performance from one session to another. Most participants made positive remarks about the final speech analysis slide, emphasizing that they found it helpful to identify which specific skills should be improved. Two participants left remarkable positive comments about the AI generated questions, mentioning that it was their

favorite aspect about Virtualspeech. Conversely, two participants did not find these questions particularly helpful because they were somewhat vague, and they felt like they were repeating what they already said in the pitch. They further explained that real-life audience questions can be more challenging.

Conclusion

Overall, the feedback collected from these nine students indicates that Virtualspeech could be a useful tool if used more recurrently. As a future step, it is recommended to test this platform on a larger sample for a longer amount of time in order to evaluate its benefits on students' public speaking skills.